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Data management plan (DMP)

Network Traces of Smart- Home Lighting Actions

NETLIGHT

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	2025-11-22	First version of the DMP – created for the Intro to RDM exercise

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Project details

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
PCAP	Packet Capture
TLS	Transport Layer Security
NETLIGHT	Network Traces of Smart-Home Lighting Actions

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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	NETLIGHT – Encrypted Smart Lighting Traffic (Industry Partner Dataset)	Other	application/vnd.tcpdump.pcap	1 - 5 GB	no

Description for "NETLIGHT – Encrypted Smart Lighting Traffic (Industry Partner Dataset)":

The raw dataset consists of packet-capture (PCAP) files recorded at the network edge of a smart-lighting system. Each PCAP contains bidirectional IP/TCP traffic between one or more lighting controllers/gateways, the vendor cloud backend and operator apps or management interfaces during normal operation and defined test scenarios. The captures include full transport/network headers and precise timestamps, but all application payloads remain encrypted (TLS/HTTPS). No payload decryption or content modification was performed.

Packets are stored exactly as observed on the wire. Filenames and external logs (not part of the PCAP itself) indicate the measurement date, scenario and involved subsystem, so the traces can be linked to specific system states and events.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	IoT-23: A labeled dataset with malicious and benign IoT network traffic	https://zenodo.org/records/4743746	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	ZigBeeNet dataset	https://zenodo.org/records/13957307	CC BY 4.0	no

Description for "IoT-23: A labeled dataset with malicious and benign IoT network traffic" from the authors:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743746> IoT-23 is a dataset of network traffic from Internet of Things (IoT) devices. It has 20 malware captures executed in IoT devices, and 3 captures for benign IoT devices traffic. It was first published in January 2020, with captures ranging from 2018 to 2019. These IoT network traffic was captured in the Stratosphere Laboratory, AIC group, FEL, CTU

University, Czech Republic. Its goal is to offer a large dataset of real and labeled IoT malware infections and IoT benign traffic for researchers to develop machine learning algorithms. This dataset and its research was funded by Avast Software. The malware was allowed to connect to the Internet.

Description for "ZigBeeNet dataset" from the authors:

We present a decrypted ZigBee IoT network traffic dataset in a smart home environment. We use 15 devices in total, six different types of devices (Hub, Power Plug, Smart Light, Smart Bulb, Wall Switch and Motion Sensor) and nine different devices. We have collected data from 20 days. The dataset is a result of our work published in the Applied Science journal: <https://zenodo.org/records/13957307>

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The primary dataset (NETLIGHT) is generated by recording raw PCAP traffic at the WAN edge of an industry smart-lighting deployment during normal operation and test campaigns. Traffic is captured on a Linux host with standard tools (tcpdump/Wireshark) and then processed with Python 3 scripts to extract packet-length and timing features per burst/flow. In addition, I conceptually reuse two open IoT traffic datasets. First, the IoT-23 dataset from the Stratosphere IPS group (CTU Prague) provides 23 scenarios of benign and malicious IoT network traffic in PCAP and derived flow formats under a CC BY licence. Second, the ZigBeeNet dataset from iitis (Polish Academy of Sciences) provides decrypted Zigbee PCAP traces from a real smart home with 15 devices over 20 days under a CC BY 4.0 licence. For both external datasets, I apply the same basic feature-extraction scripts to small subsets of their PCAP files and compare the resulting feature distributions to my own NETLIGHT data

The original datasets remain hosted and distributed by their providers. For reused data, I rely on the existing open licences. IoT-23 is published under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) licence by Stratosphere IPS

ZigBeeNet is released under a CC BY 4.0 licence by its authors. I do not redistribute these datasets

I only store local copies (or derived feature tables) for analysis and cite the original datasets and DOIs according to their licence terms.

2. Documentatio performed packets and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The data are organised in a simple project tree: `data_raw/` (PCAPs), `data_processed/` (CSV/JSON tables), `results/` (text/plots), `code/` (scripts) and `docs/` (DMP, notes). Filenames follow the project naming convention documented in `README_data.md` and include device, action and a timestamp. Scripts are versioned with Git, published dataset snapshots in the repository are given simple version labels.

I will enter standard repository metadata: title and acronym, short abstract, keywords, creators (with affiliation and ORCID where available), licence, measurement dates and a short description of devices and protocols. Inside the archive, `README_data.md` documents the experiment, directory layout, file naming and column meanings

`README_code.md` documents the scripts and required software. CSV/JSON files use self-explanatory English column names so the data can be understood without the original environment. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

Documentation is kept lightweight but reproducible. README_data.md explains what each file contains, how the captures were produced and how to interpret the tables. README_code.md describes the scripts, their dependencies and the basic workflow from raw PCAP files to processed tables and the evaluation output file. With these two READMEs and the repository metadata, another researcher can rerun the scripts on the PCAPs and check that they obtain the same processed data and results.

2b Data quality control

The main quality checks are:

- running repeated captures for the same scenario to detect obvious outliers,
- checking that each PCAP contains the expected device and time window,
- verifying that processed CSV tables have no missing timestamps and that basic statistics (packet counts, durations) match the underlying PCAPs.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Paul Anton Mairinger (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (NETLIGHT – Encrypted Smart Lighting Traffic (Industry Partner Dataset)) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute’s administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: For the primary NETLIGHT dataset, TU Wien and the industry partner jointly hold rights according to our collaboration agreement; Paul Mairinger acts as depositor on behalf of TU Wien. Access settings for P1 in the institutional repository are governed by this agreement and the NDA.

The IoT-23 and ZigBeeNet datasets remain the intellectual property of their original authors and are reused under their CC BY 4.0 licences.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-23	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: No proprietary tools needed. All used Tools are open source and publicly available.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

Paul Anton Mairinger will coordinate data management for this small project and keep the DMP up to date. He is responsible for producing metadata, organising backups and ensuring that the anonymised derived dataset (P2) is deposited in the repository.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.